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***Bucculatrix ulmicola* Kuznetsov, 1962, *Phyllonorycter cerris* (Gregor, 1952) and *Notocelia mediterranea* (Obraztsov, 1952) – new records for the Hungarian fauna (Lepidoptera: Bucculatricidae, Gracillariidae, Tortricidae)**

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Abstract. The study introduces three species of micro-moths previously unknown in Hungary: *Bucculatrix ulmicola* Kuznetsov, 1962, *Phyllonorycter cerris* (Gregor, 1952) and *Notocelia mediterranea* (Obraztsov, 1952). It analyses the taxonomy, diagnosis, bionomics, and geographical distribution of species. Describes the habitus and genital structure of species. The locations of the species are shown on maps. It is concluded that, based on these studies, all three species are new to the Hungarian fauna.

Keywords. Geographical distribution, bionomics, new records, Hungary.

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Introduction

According to the most recent Hungarian Microlepidoptera checklist (Pastorális & Buschmann 2018), 2313 species are known in the country. However, the Hungarian fauna has continued to grow and in the five years since that publication several new species have been added, many being published in this journal.

In Hungary, Slovakia, and Czechia, several lepidopterologists have been collecting regularly and successfully for many years. In this paper, with their help, we present three new species from Hungary alongside relevant bionomics, geographical distribution and features for identification.

Material and methods

Specimens were collected by a variety of methods during the day and at lights during the night. Genitalia dissections were done in accordance with Robinson (1976); others are preserved in micro-vials filled with glycerol. The specimens examined are housed in the collections indicated in the text. All published data included under the References in this paper have been critically analysed.

Bucculatricidae

1. *Bucculatrix ulmicola* Kuznetsov, 1962

Examined materials: Söréd (18.25°E, 47.31°N), 17.v.2008, 1♂ (Gp Ig. Richter 16276); Hungary, Csákberény, Bucka-hegy (18.28°E, 47.35°N), 11.v.2007, 1♂ + 1♀ (Gp Ig. Richter ♂ 744, Gp Z. Tokár ♀ 11665), all leg. & coll. Ig. Richter; 11.v.2019, mines and larvae on *Ulmus minor*, leg. & coll. Z. Tokár; 6.vii.2019, 1♂ (Gp Z. Tokár ♂ 13754), and empty mines on *Ulmus minor*, leg., coll. & all det. Z. Tokár. **A new species in Hungary.**

The species was described by Kuznetsov (1962) based on specimens from Central Asia (Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan) and Transcaucasia (Armenia). The holotype and allotype are from Turkmenistan, Magtymguly (formerly Kara-Kala), reared from larvae found on *Ulmus* sp. (probably *U. parvifolia* Jacq. or *U. pumila* L.).

The author writes in the description that *B. ulmicola* was previously well-known as a pest of elms in parks and forests. He cites the work of Mityaev (1955), who describes in detail the biology of this species in Kazakhstan, using the species name *Bucculatrix ulmiella* Ger. (Gerasimov). Most likely, A. M. Gerasimov planned to describe the species, but under a different name (below the labels of the holotype and allotype of *B. ulmicola* there is a handwritten label “*Bucculatrix kirgisica* Grsm in litt.”), but his death at a young age during World War II, in 1942, was very probably the reason why the description was not realized.

B. ulmicola was later reported from the south of European Russia and from Crimea (Seksjaeva 1993) and further records from Central Asia (Tajikistan) were added by Puplesis et al. (1996).

In external appearance and genitalia, *B. ulmicola* (Figure 1) resembles the closely related *B. ulmifoliae* Hering, 1931 and this similarity caused frequent mistakes in the correct identification of the species. For example, drawings of the genitalia of *B. ulmifoliae* in Varenne and Nel (2014) and Baniameri et al. (2017) belong to *B. ulmicola*. Apart from *B. ulmifoliae*, *B. ulmicola* is also similar in appearance to two other European species – *B. caspica* Puplesis & Sruoga, 1991 and *B. ulmella* Zeller, 1848.

Figure 1–4. 1. *Bucculatrix ulmicola*, Hungary, Csákberény, Bucka-hegy, 11.v.2007, leg., coll. & photo Ig. Richter; 2. Mines and larvae of *Bucculatrix ulmicola* on a leaf of *Ulmus minor*; 3. Larva in a moulting cocoon (11.v.2019, Bucka-hegy, photos Z. Tokár); 4. Locality with *Ulmus minor* trees in Hungary, Csákberény, Bucka-hegy (6.vii.2019, photo Z. Tokár)

Figure 5–7. 5. Male genitalia of *Bucculatrix ulmicola*, Hungary, Csákberény, Bucka-hegy, 11.v.2007, Gp. Richter 744, drawing Z. Tokár, scale bar 0.2 mm; Kuznetsov's drawings of male (6) and female genitalia (7) of *Bucculatrix ulmicola* from the species description article (1962).

Through the study of the third author of this article, it was possible to identify older collection material of *B. ulmicola*, similarly misidentified or unspecified, from Greece, Macedonia and Romania. Further misidentified material is also known from Bulgaria, Hungary, Slovakia, Ukraine and Iran (Tokár et al. 2021; Rajaei et al. 2023; Liu et al. in press). A study of paratypes from Armenia and Kazakhstan, from the type series deposited in the museum collections of the Zoological Institute of Russian Academy of Sciences in Petersburg, which were kindly provided by Dr Svetlana Baryshnikova, helped to correctly identify this species.

For many specimens of *B. ulmicola*, examination of the copulatory organs is recommended for proper identification. Males can be easily distinguished by the shape of the valva, aedeagus and a small process on the socius lateral lobe (Figure 5) and females mainly by the oval shape of the ostium (Figure 7). It should be noted that Kuznetsov's drawing of the male genitalia (Figure 6) does not show the socius process, characteristic for this species. These can be seen, for example, in Baryshnikova's drawing in her paper from 2013.

Biology. Several species of elms *Ulmus* L. (Ulmaceae) are mentioned as food plants for *B. ulmicola* (Mityaev 1955, Kuznetsov 1962, Puplesis et al. 1996). In Central and Southern Europe, *Ulmus minor* Mill. has been observed as its host plant. The moth has two generations in Central Europe and in warmer areas (Central Asia, Iran) up to 3 generations per year.

Young larvae are leaf miners, forming narrow, characteristic mines (Figure 2). Adult larvae leave the mines and spin silky nets on the surface of the leaf (“cocoonets”, or moulting cocoons) (Figure 3). Then they live openly on the leaves, skeletonizing them from the underside, later making holes in the leaves. They pupate in grey-white ribbed cocoons on leaves or tree trunks in cracks of the bark. Individuals of the 2nd or 3rd (in warm areas) generation overwinter in the pupal stage.

Adults have been collected from April to October; in Central Europe reports are from the beginning of May to the end of August.

The third author was able to find mines and larvae on *Ulmus minor* leaves on May 11, 2019, at Bucka-hegy near Csákberény (Figures 2, 3). On a later visit on July 6, 2019, he found only empty mines on the leaves but managed to attract one specimen to the light trap in the evening. Even earlier, in May 2007, Ignác Richter caught 2 specimens of *B. ulmicola* at the same location and a year later, one specimen in May 2008 at a nearby location in a vicinity of Söréd.

The specimens found in Hungary as well as in Slovakia (NR Vřšok near Štúrovo) indicate that *B. ulmicola* prefers warm, xerothermic localities, in contrast to the related *B. ulmifoliae*, which prefers more closed and moist places with elms. Figure 4 shows the community of *Ulmus minor* on the southern slope of the Bucka-hegy hill.

Distribution in Hungary. So far, only two males and two females are known from Hungary: Söréd (18.25°E, 47.31°N); Csákberény, Bucka-hegy (18.28°E, 47.35°N); in coll. Ig. Richter and Z. Tokár. For detailed data, see the chapter "Examined materials".

Söréd and Csákberény are in the Vértes Mountains, which lie in north-western Hungary, in the Central Transdanubian region and between the Bakony and Gerecse. Geologically, the Vértes constitute a uniform structure. On the surface, there are no rocks older than those of the mid-Triassic and the dominant rock overall is dolomite, from the Upper Triassic. All the layers are ancient marine deposits. The average altitude above sea level is 350 metres with a peak of about 480 m. Typical forests of these Mountains are oak-hornbeam (like *Quercus petraeae Carpinetum*) and in cooler zones beech (*Fagio medio-europaeum*). On the southern slopes of dolomite grasslands, dolomite bush forests and Pubescent Oak forests grow. At the foot of the hills and in the brook valleys, willow, alder woodlands and marshy meadows are the typical plant associations.

General distribution. Scattered distribution from France through southern Europe and the south of Central Europe, Ukraine, the south of the European part of Russia, Transcaucasia to Central Asia and Iran.

Gracillariidae

2. *Phyllonorycter cerris* (Gregor, 1952)

Examined material: Hungary, Öskü, 1 ex. e.l. in *Quercus cerris*, iv.1983; Balatonudvari, 1 ex. e. l. in *Quercus cerris*, iii.1988; leg. A. Laštůvka. **A new species in Hungary.**

Gregor (1952) noticed that the adults of *Phyllonorycter quercifoliella* (Zeller, 1839), which he bred from *Quercus cerris*, looked quite different externally to those bred from *Quercus robur*, *Q. petraea*, or *Q. pubescens*. Since he did not find any genital differences, he continued to count them as the same species, but did not describe them as eco-variants or simply forma but, even though the context did not fit, as a new subspecies ("*Lith. quercifoliella* ssp. *cerris* ssp. n.") so that the name became available. In the following decades, the taxon was either kept as a subspecies or was ignored entirely. Only Laštůvka et al. (2018) consistently list the taxon as a species: Given the barcoding differences and sympatric occurrence, there is almost no other interpretation. This classification as a species is supported by Lopez-Vaamonde et al. (2021) in their checklist of the Gracillariidae of Europe.

According to Laštůvka et al. (2018) it is known in the warm oak forests, parks in southern parts of Central and South-eastern Europe, in Central Europe from the Czech Republic, eastern

Figures 8–9. Adults; 8. *Phyllonorycter cerris* 9. *Ph. quercifoliella* (Graphics made by Ales Laštůvka)

Austria, southern and eastern Slovakia and Hungary. Within the Czech Republic it is only known locally in southern Moravia northwards to Brno. It is believed to be related to the natural occurrence of the turkey oaks, but the species was also found in some artificially established *Quercus cerris* stands in northern parts of the Czech Republic, both in northern Moravia and in northern Bohemia (see Lepiforum 2023).

Tortricidae

3. *Notocelia mediterranea* (Obraztsov, 1952) | A new species in Hungary.

Examined material: 1 ♀, Hungary, Bajna, Epöl, 17.vi.2006, leg. J. Skyva (GP 202430); 1 ♀, Hungary, Csákberény, 18.viii.2000, J. Skyva.

Diagnosis. The imago's habitus has not yet been published. Wingspan 14–19 mm. According to the original description reminiscent of *Notocelia incarnatana* (Hübner, [1799–1800]). Several experts take a different view of Obraztsov's description. The apex of the forewing of females is rounded (Figure 10). The basic wing colour is whitish, lighter than the *N. incarnatana* species, lacking the reddish markings and not different in size from the males, or larger. There is little variation in the genitalia, so the morphology of the species needs further research.

Bionomy. So far, it is known in one generation, with imagoes are collected in August and September. The species prefers steppe meadows, rocky grasslands, and old forest edges habitats.

Distribution. For a long time, it was known only from Sicily and the area around Rome, but according to recent research it is also present in Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, France, Hungary, Montenegro, Slovakia, and Spain (Tokár et al. 2021).

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Figures 10–11. **10.** *Notocelia mediterranea*, female, Hungary, Csákberény, 18.viii.2000, leg. J. Skyva (Photo: J. Šumpich). **11.** *Notocelia incarnatana*, wing pattern of male, Hungary, Villány Hills, Nagyharsány, 02.ix.1986. leg. I. Fazekas (Photo: I. Fazekas). The species is local in Hungary, in mountainous areas. It is rare on the plains (e.g. Tápió region). Its southernmost occurrence is in the calcareous open rock grasslands of the Villány Hills, under the intense Mediterranean influence.

Notes. Re-examination of collections should not be restricted to *N. incarnatana*, since *E. mediterranea* specimens have also been found among material labelled as *Epinotia cinereana* (Haworth, 1811). The bionomics and geographic distribution of this species are less well-known. It is found in: Bulgaria, the Czech Republic, France, Croatia, Hungary, Montenegro, Spain, and Slovakia.

Figures 12–14. 12. Male genitalia of *Notocelia mediterranea*; 13. Male genitalia of *Notocelia incarnatana*; 14. Female genitalia of *Notocelia incarnatana* (after Razowski 2003, with additions and indications).

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Special thanks go to our colleagues Jan Skyva (CZ-Prague) for providing data and the figures on *Notocelia mediterranea* and Aleš Laštůvka (CZ-Prostějov) for providing data on *Phyllonorycter cerris* for publication, and Jan Šumpich (CZ-Prague) for all their help and support. We thank Colin W. Plant (UK-Bishops Stortford) for his linguistic corrections and comments on a draft of this paper.

Figures 15–17. Geographical distribution of the species in Hungary:
14. *Bucculatrix ulmicola*; **15.** *Phyllonorycter cerris*; **16.** *Notocelia mediterranea*.
It is likely that the distribution of the species is much larger, so further studies are needed.

Összefoglalás

A *Bucculatrix ulmicola* Kuznetsov, 1962, a *Phyllonorycter cerris* (Gregor, 1952) és a *Notocelia mediterranea* (Obraztsov, 1952) új fajok a magyar faunában (Lepidoptera: Bucculatricidae, Gracillariidae, Tortricidae)

Fazekas Imre, Pastorális Gábor & Tokár Zdenko

A tanulmány három, Magyarországon eddig ismeretlen molylepke fajt mutat be: *Bucculatrix ulmicola* Kuznetsov, 1962 a *Phyllonorycter cerris* (Gregor, 1952) és a *Notocelia mediterranea* (Obraztsov, 1952). Elemzi a fajok taxonómiáját, diagnózisát, bionómiáját és földrajzi elterjedését. Leírja a fajok habitusát és genitália felépítését. A fajok előfordulási helyeit térképeken mutatja be. A vizsgálatok alapján megállapítja, hogy mindhárom faj új a magyar faunában.

1. *Bucculatrix ulmicola* Kuznetsov, 1962 – Javasolt magyar név: hegyi szilfa-bordásmoly
A fajt Kuznetsov (1962) írta le közép-ázsiai (Türkmenisztán, Üzbegisztán, Kazahsztán) és transzkaukázusi (Örményország) példányok alapján. A holotípus és az allotípus Türkmenisztánból, Magtymgulyból (korábban Kara-Kala) származik, *Ulmus* spp. (valószínűleg *U. parvifolia* Jacq. vagy *U. pumila* L.) fajon talált lárvákból nevelve.

Area: szétszórt elterjedés Franciaországtól Dél-Európán és Közép-Európa déli részében, továbbá Ukrajnában, az európai Oroszország déli tájain, valamint Transzkaukázián át egészen Közép-Ázsiáig és Iránig.

Hatalmas földrajzi elterjedési területén az imágókat többnyire áprilistól októberig gyűjtötték. Közép-Európából eddig csak május elejétől augusztus végéig jelentették. A harmadik szerző 2019. május 11-én a Csákberény melletti Bucka-hegyen, az *Ulmus minor* leveleken aknákat és lárvákat gyűjtött. Egy későbbi, 2019. július 6-i látogatásakor csak üres aknákat talált a leveleken, de egy példányt sikerült a fénycsapdába csalogatnia. Még korábban, 2007 májusában Richter Ignác ugyanezen a helyen két példányt fogott a *B. ulmicola*-ból, egy évvel később, 2008 májusában pedig egy további példány keült elő Söréd közelében.

2. *Phyllonorycter cerris* (Gregor, 1952) – Javasolt magyar név: csertölgylevél-sátorosmoly
Gregor (1952) megfigyelte, hogy a *Phyllonorycter quercifoliella* kifejlett példányai, amelyeket *Quercus cerris*-ből tenyésztett ki, külsőleg teljesen másképp néznek ki, mint amelyeket a *Quercus robur*-ból, *Q. petraea*-ból vagy a *Q. pubescens*-ből tenyésztették ki. Mivel nem talált genitália különbségeket, továbbra is ugyanahhoz a fajhoz sorolta őket, de nem ökológiai változatnak vagy egyszerűen formának írta le azokat, hanem új alfajként ("*Lith. quercifoliella* ssp. *cerris* ssp. n."), így a név elérhetővé vált. A következő évtizedekben a taxont vagy alfajként tartották nyilván, vagy teljesen figyelmen kívül hagyták. Csak Laštůvka et al. (2018) nevezték meg a taxont következetesen fajként.

Laštůvka et al. (2018) szerint Közép-Európában Csehországból, Kelet-Ausztriából, Dél- és Kelet-Szlovákiából továbbá Magyarországról (Öskü, Balatonudvari) és Délkelet-Európából ismert a meleg tölgyerdőkben, parkokban.

3. *Notocelia mediterranea* (Obraztsov, 1952) – Javasolt magyar név: olasz tükrösmoly
Földrajzi elterjedéséről még keveset tudunk, mivel könnyen felcserélhető a hasonló fajokkal. A gyűjtemények újbóli revíziója során genitália vizsgálata a *Notocelia incarnatana* és az *Epinotia cinereana* néven címkézett anyagok között is megtaláltak az *E. mediterranea* példányokat. E faj bionómiája és földrajzi elterjedése kevésbé ismert. Sokáig csak Szicíliából és Róma környékéről volt ismert, de a legújabb kutatások szerint Bulgáriában, Horvátországban, Csehországban, Franciaországban, Magyarországon, Montenegróban, Szlovákiában és Spanyolországban is jelen van (Tokár et al. 2021). Eddig egy generációban ismert, az imágókat augusztusban és szeptemberben gyűjtötték. Habitat: a faj a sztyeppréteket, sziklagyepeket és az öreg erdők szegélyeit preferálja.

References

- Baniameri V., Maleki S. & Alipanah H. 2017: Morphology and biology of the elm leaf-mining moth, *Bucculatrix ulmifoliae* Hering, 1931 (Lep.: Bucculatricidae) in Iran. – Journal of Entomological Society of Iran 37(2): 213–222.
- Baryshnikova S. V. 2013: Bucculatricid moths (Lepidoptera, Bucculatricidae) of the fauna of Russia and adjacent territories. – Keys to the fauna of Russia published by the Zoological Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences 175: 1–160. [in Russian]
- Gregor F. 1952: Moli rodu *Lithocolletis* Hb. na dubech v ČSR. The quercicolous *Lithocolletis* Hb. in ČSR. – Zoologické a entomologické listy 1: 24–56, 11 pls.
- Lopez-Vaamonde C., Kirichenko N., Cama A., Doorenweerd C., Godfray H.C.J., Guiguet A., Gomboc S., Huemer P., Landry J.-F., Laštůvka A., Laštůvka Z., Lee K.M., Lees D.C., Mutanen M., van Nieukerken E.J., Segerer A.H., Triberti P., Wieser C. & Rougerie R. 2021: Evaluating DNA Barcoding for Species Identification and Discovery in European Gracillariid Moths. – Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution 9 (Artikel 626752): 1–16.
- Trematerra P. 2003: Catalogo dei Lepidoptera Tortricidae della fauna italiana: geonomia, distribuzione in Italia, note biologiche, identificazione. – Bollettino di Zoologia agraria e di Bachicoltura, Ser. II, 35 (suppl. 1): 1–270.
- Kuznetsov V. 1962: Il'movaya krivousaya mol' *Bucculatrix [sic] ulmicola* Kuznetz. sp. n. (Lepidoptera, Bucculatricidae [sic]) vreditel' il'mov v Zakavkaz'e i Srednei Azii. – Doklady Akademii Nauk Armiyanskoi SSR 35(2): 81–83. [in Russian]
- Laštůvka A., Laštůvka Z., Liška J. & Šumpich J. 2018: Motýli a housenky střední Evropy V. Drobní motýli I. – Akademia Praha, 532 p.
- Lepiforum e. V. (Hrsg.) (2005–2023): Bestimmungshilfe für die in Europa nachgewiesenen Schmetterlingsarten. Version 26, 26–29. April 2021. <http://www.lepiforum.de/>
- Liu T., Tokár Z. & Yan J. in press: Revision of *Bucculatrix* Zeller, 1839 associated with *Ulmus*, with description of one new species from China (Lepidoptera, Bucculatricidae).
- Mityaev I.D. 1955: Materialy po biologii il'movoi moli (*Bucculatrix ulmiella* Ger.). – Akademiya nauk Kazachskoi SSR. Trudy Instituta zoologii, IV: 218–222. [in Russian]
- Pastoralis G. & Buschmann F. 2018: Checklist of the Hungarian micro-moths, 2018 (Lepidoptera). – Microlepidoptera.hu 14: 77–258. DOI: 10.24386/Microlep.2018.14.77
- Puplesis R., Diškus A., Noreika R. & Saparmamedova N. 1996: Revised check-list of mining Lepidoptera (Nepticuloidea, Tischerioidea and Gracillarioidea) from Central Asia. – Tijdschrift voor Entomologie 139(2): 191–200.
- Rajaei H., Aarvik L., Arnscheid W.R., Baldizzone G., Bartsch D., Bengtsson B. Å., Bidzilya O., Buchner P., Buchsbaum U., Buszko J., Dubatolov V., Erlacher S., Esfandiari M., Freina J. de, Gaedike R., Gyulai P., Hausmann A., Haxaire J., Hobern D., Hofmann A., Ignatev N., Kaila L., Kallies A., Keil T., Kiss Á., Kitching I. J., Kun A., László G. M., Leraut G., Mally R., Matov A., Meineke J-U., Melichar T., Mey W., Mironov V., Müller B., Naderi A., Nässig W.A., Naumann S., Nazari V., Nieukerken E. J. van, Nuss M., Pöll N., Prozorov A. M., Rabieh M. M., Rákossy L., Rindoš M., Rota J., Rougerie R., Schintlmeister A., Shirvani A., Sihvonen P., Simonsen T.J., Sinev S.Yu., Skou P., Sobczyk T., Sohn J.-C., Tabell J., Tarmann G., Tokár Z., Trusch R., Varga Z., Volynkin A. V., Wanke D., Yakovlev R. V., Zahiri R., Zehzad P., Zeller H.C., Zolotuhin V.V. & Karsholt O. (2023): Catalogue of the Lepidoptera of Iran. – In: Rajaei H. & Karsholt O. (eds.): Lepidoptera Iranica. – Integrative systematics 6 (Special Issue): 121–461.
- Razowski J. 2003: Tortricidae of Europe. Volume 2, Olethreutinae. – František Slamka, Bratislava, 301 p.
- Seksjaeva S. V. 1993: Obzor krivousyh krohotok-molei (Lepidoptera, Bucculatricidae) fauny Rossii (Review of the mining moths (Lepidoptera, Bucculatricidae) of the fauna of Russia). – Trudy Zoologicheskogo Instituta RAN 255: 99–120. [in Russian]
- Šumpich J., Liška J., Laštůvka Z. & Laštůvka A. 2022: Motýli a housenky střední Evropy VI. Drobní motýli II. – Praha (Academia), 811 p.
- Tokár Z., Šumpich J., Laštůvka A., Laštůvka Z., Liška J., Elsner G., Lendel A., Štefanovič R. & Richter Ig. 2021: Nové druhy drobných motýľov (Microlepidoptera) pre faunu Slovenska. / Species of small moths (Microlepidoptera) new for the fauna of Slovakia. – Entomofauna carpathica 33(2): 1–20.
- Varenne T. & Nel J. 2014: Quatre nouveaux Microlépidoptères pour la faune de France (Lepidoptera Psychidae, Bucculatricidae, Autostichidae et Pylalidae). – Alexanor 25: 489–493.